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REPORTING VERBS IN KAZAKH ACADEMIC DISCOURSE: EXAMPLES FROM THE CORPUS

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ABSTRACT

This study is pioneering in its investigation of citation practices in academic writing in Kazakh, with a particular focus on reporting verbs. The analysis is based on a corpus of 110 research articles from eleven disciplines written by native Kazakh speakers. The Kazakh scholarly community employs a significant number of reporting verbs in their academic writing. The analysis of the concordances of these verbs has revealed structural and discourse patterns specific to Kazakh. Lexemes with a signalling function come alongside reporting verbs and indicate the direction of discourse development in terms of the writer's stance and level of engagement. Reporting verbs in Kazakh include research, cognitive, and discourse actions, and these types have varying degrees of occurrence in academic writing. Despite writers opting to present referenced work in largely identical ways, the study discovered disciplinary disparities in the total usage of reporting verbs, the frequencies of individual items, and the preferences for particular rhetorical categories. The results and findings of this study are valuable as theoretical and teaching material in corpus linguistics and discourse studies. The findings reported from this study, as well as the verb lists, can be used by teachers and learners of the Kazakh language to expand or establish authorial voice in different academic writings.

KEYWORDS: Reporting Verbs, Citation, Kazakh, Academic Discourse, Academic Text, Discipline, Variations, Corpus-Based Analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

Citing previous research is an important feature of academic writing. In scholarly writing, writers refer to theories, ideas, concepts, and findings from another research. Knowledge is displayed and integrated through referencing, which is a system of formally acknowledging the sources of other writers' words and thoughts (Borg, 2000, p. 4). References serve to reinforce a point, present an argument, and persuade the reader. The purpose of referencing prior research is not only to acknowledge the work of others but also to support the writer's own claims to knowledge (Petric, 2007). Academic writers are expected to cite sources for a variety of reasons, such as incorporating other researchers' ideas into their arguments, demonstrating what is already known about the topic of study, highlighting flaws in other people's arguments, or aligning themselves with a specific camp, school, or group (Thompson and Tribble, 2001, p. 92). Situating the current work within a broader disciplinary narrative is key to the success of academic writing (Berkenkotter and Huckin, 1995; Hyland, 2000; Hyland, 2002; Myers, 1990). Without such links, academics would be unable to justify their arguments by connecting their research activities to significant work in the field or use this disciplinary knowledge to demonstrate the originality of their position (Berkenkotter and Huckin, 1995; Hyland, 2002). Therefore, making appropriate references to the work of others, reporting their actions and ideas, and supporting one's own claims to knowledge are all essential parts of academic writing.

EAP (English for Academic Purposes) instructors have paid a great deal of attention to references in academic discourse. In the early 1980s, Swales (1981) focused specifically on the introductions of articles. A decade later, Thompson and Ye (1991) also examined the introductions of academic papers in order to analyse the use of reporting verbs in citations. EAP teachers recognise that conveying the conventions of referencing in academic writing is challenging for non-native English students. Non-native English speakers often struggle to use references effectively in academic reading and writing. Even native English speakers may lack citation competence. They also find it difficult to integrate source materials appropriately (Campbell, 1990; Borg, 2000) and struggle to use citations effectively in their writing and reading (Matalene, 1985; Thompson and Ye, 1991; Pennycook, 1996; Hyland, 2002). However, Liu *et al.* (2016) argue that second language (L2) writers are at the greatest disadvantage due to cultural and linguistic

differences. Non-native English writers often overuse quotations without interpretation (Bruce 1989) and use a limited range of verbs to introduce them (Pickard, 1993; Hyland, 2002). EAP instructors constantly note that non-native speakers of English overuse the reporting verb 'say'. For example, Pickard (1993) reports that the verb 'say' is used excessively. This overuse is indicative not only of limited vocabulary, but also of a broader issue concerning understanding academic writing requirements, particularly with regard to acknowledging sources (Pickard, 1995, p. 89). This view is also echoed by Hyland (2002), noting that the limited use of verbs can often be referred to not due to a lack of vocabulary but rather as a symptom of a problem with how to properly use sources in academic writing. Similarly, McEnery and Kifle (2002) found that L2 writers tended to use fewer assertive devices than native speakers (McEnery and Kifle, 2002). Non-native English speakers may find it challenging to select a reporting verb that meets the grammatical requirements of their sentences and, perhaps more crucially, conveys their opinion on the claims (Borg, 2000).

Substantial cultural differences exist in the use of references (Bloch, 2010), which also relate to their appropriate use in academic writing and to plagiarism (Thompson and Tribble, 2001). Students with a cultural orientation to memorisation may not be familiar with the conventions of academic citation, which can lead to writing that appears to be plagiarised (Pennycook, 1996; Yang and Lin, 2009). Hyland (1999) provides several developmental and cultural explanations for the problem. One such reason is that students are rarely taught how to express their own views clearly on these types of claims (Hyland, 1999). As referencing is such a crucial part of academic writing, it is beneficial to equip students with the necessary skills (Hyland, 2002). In order to become successful academic writers, it is necessary to understand how grammatical choices when reporting claims can affect credibility as a researcher as well as enhance the rhetorical impact of the claim (Bloch, 2010). Thus, a key element of pedagogy for academic writing should be teaching students how to use reporting verbs to achieve their rhetorical goals (Swales and Feak, 2004).

The use of reporting verbs by researchers in academic writing may vary depending on their level of experience. There are certainly differences between novice writers and expert writers in the way they refer to theories, ideas, concepts, and findings from other research in their own work. Pickard (1995)

found that novice writers tend to overuse particular items in their references, such as 'say', and she is interested to find out expert writers' citation practices. Making references to the literature can be a significant challenge for novice writers (Campbell, 1990; Borg, 2000). They may struggle because they are not at the right stage of cognitive or intellectual development (Britton, et al. 1975; Pennycook, 1996) or due to cultural factors (Fox, 1994; Connor, 1996; Thompson and Tribble, 2001). Failure to acknowledge the source of ideas may result in accusations of plagiarism, while inexperienced phrasing of reporting statements may lead to ambiguous or misleading indications of the stance of both the writer and the cited author (Groom, 2000).

The Kazakh language has a significant number of verbs used in citations, and their semantics and functions are diverse. Reporting verbs in particular, and citations in general, have not been the focus of much research in Kazakh linguistics. While the substantial body of research published on reporting verbs in English, Kazakh linguistics lacks such studies. Kazakh academic discourse has received little linguistic or pedagogical attention, and no studies have examined reporting verbs. This study aims to shed light on the verbs used in Kazakh citations. It is pioneering in its analysis of reporting verbs in Kazakh academic writing. The objective is to identify a specific subset of lexical items: reporting verbs used in citations. Furthermore, analysing these verbs will help us to identify the linguistic and discourse patterns specific to Kazakh reporting verbs.

2. REPORTING VERBS IN ACADEMIC DISCOURSE

In academic writing, reporting verbs play a crucial role in integrating and evaluating the work of other scholars. Reporting verbs are one of the grammatical devices that writers use to express their stance in an academic paper (Hyland, 1998). They can be used to report one's own claims or ideas, as well as to demonstrate one's attitude towards the claims of others (Thompson and Ye, 1991). Reporting verbs enable researchers to accurately convey the ideas, findings and arguments of previous studies, while also signalling their own stance towards those sources, whether it be agreement, disagreement or neutrality. Common academic reporting verbs include *argue*, *claim*, *suggest*, *demonstrate*, *point out*, *contend*, and *maintain*, each carrying subtle nuances of meaning that reflect the writer's interpretation of the cited material.

Reporting verbs are used in integral and non-

integral citations. An integral citation is one in which the researcher's name occurs as a sentence element in the actual citation; in a non-integral citation, the researcher's name occurs in parentheses or is referred to elsewhere by a superscript number or some other device (Swales, 1990, p. 148). The choice between these two structures depends on whether the emphasis is on the reported author or the reported message. The extract below from Swales' (1981) work demonstrates a typical structure with reporting verbs in English:

Meadows and O'Conner (1971) analysed 10,000 references in the astronomy and space science literature and found 1,300 self-citations; an overall 10-15 per cent self-citational level is also probable in the applied linguistics literature, although there are wide individual variations. (p. 40)

This structure not only introduces the cited idea but also helps build the author's argument by showing how external sources support, challenge, or refine their position. Choosing the appropriate verb is essential, as it influences the perceived strength and certainty of the claim being reported.

Furthermore, reporting verbs can be categorised according to the stance they convey: positive (e.g., *hold*, *know*, *understand*), negative (e.g., *complain*, *dispute*, *blame*), or neutral (e.g., *conceive*, *anticipate*, *reflect*). (Thompson 2001; Hyland, 2002). This categorisation helps maintain a balanced and critical tone, which is highly valued in academic discourse. Carefully selecting reporting verbs enhances the clarity, precision and persuasiveness of researchers' writing, demonstrating their engagement with existing literature and their ability to think critically and independently.

Reporting verbs are involved in three distinguishable processes: 1. Research (Real-world) Acts, 2. Cognition Acts, and 3. Discourse Acts (Thompson and Ye, 1991; Hyland, 2002). Each of these processes reflects a different way of constructing and representing knowledge in academic discourse.

1. *Research (Real-World) Acts.* Research (real-world) acts refer to the actual empirical or theoretical activities that scholars perform in the course of their inquiry, such as conducting experiments, carrying out surveys, observing phenomena, or analysing existing datasets. They typically appear either in statements of findings (e.g., *analyse*, *compute*, *assay*, *explore*, *plot*, *recover*) or procedures (e.g., *observe*, *discover*, *notice*, *show*) (Hyland, 2002, p. 6). In this sense, reporting verbs act as a link between the practical research activities and their linguistic representation in the academic

discourse.

2. *Cognition Acts*. Cognition acts concern the mental processes through which scholars interpret, evaluate and understand data, theories or prior studies. These include activities such as *believe, assume, consider, conceptualise, suspect, judge, interpret, understand, recognise, and conclude*. These verbs relate to the thought processes of the researcher. Thompson and Ye (1991) identified this category as 'mental processes', encompassing all verbs related to cognition. Thompson (2001) did not name this group. Instead, he classified these verbs as 'other' and explained that some verbs in the corpus did not fit neatly into the first two categories. In many academic contexts, cognition-orientated reporting verbs are important because they show how authors weigh evidence, construct hypotheses, or critique earlier work. They therefore help readers to understand the author's intellectual process and the degree of certainty or caution attached to particular claims.

3. *Discourse Acts*. These verbs (e.g., *speak, talk, discuss, converse*) relate to verbal communication. These involve linguistic activities and focus on verbalising cognitive or research processes (e.g., *ascribe, discuss, hypothesise, report, state*). Thompson and Ye (1991) refer to them as 'textual' verbs, whereas Thompson (2001) and Hyland (2002) prefer the term 'discourse'. Discourse-orientated reporting verbs help structure the discussion, guide the reader's attention, and position the current study within the broader scholarly conversation. They also contribute to the author's voice and stance, allowing the writer to align, distance, or qualify themselves from previous positions depending on the chosen verb.

Together, these three processes - research (real-world) acts, cognition acts, and discourse acts - show that reporting verbs are not merely neutral grammatical tools but active components in the construction, interpretation, and textual presentation of knowledge in academic discourse.

2.1. Evaluative Functions Of Reporting Verbs

Writers of academic texts have a purpose in constructing their text, which is conveyed through their choice of information and how it is presented. Focusing only on the information provided and taking it at face value often results in missing or misinterpreting the purpose. Evaluation in a text signal this purpose (Thompson and Ye 1991, p. 367). The relationship between evaluation and reporting verbs is well established. Thompson and Ye (1991) have investigated evaluation in reporting verbs. They have distinguished between the writer, who is

the author of the text, and the author who is cited by the writer. Within the process categories, writers made more nuanced decisions, using reporting verbs to adopt a supportive, tentative, critical, or neutral stance towards the claims being reported (Hyland, 2002).

In reporting, evaluation is conveyed through the use of *factive, non-factive* and *counter-factive* verbs (Thompson and Ye, 1991; Hyland, 2002). Writers can express their acceptance of authors' results or conclusions using *factive* verbs such as *demonstrate, establish, show, solve* or *confirm*. Alternatively, they can take a counterfactual stance and portray the authors' judgements as false or incorrect using verbs such as *fail, misunderstand, ignore* or *overlook*. A final option is to comment on research findings non-factively, providing no clear indication as to their reliability (e.g., *find, identify, observe, obtain*).

In the Cognition Act, verbs portray the cited work in terms of a mental process and handle evaluation differently. Rather than taking an explicit personal stance on the reported information or opinion, writers attribute a particular attitude to the cited author (Hyland, 2002). They can depict the author as having a positive attitude towards the subject matter by using verbs such as *agree, concur, hold, know, think* or *understand* to convey acceptance of its truth or accuracy. Alternatively, authors may be characterised as having a tentative view of the reported matter by using verbs such as *believe, doubt, speculate, suppose* or *suspect*. Rarely, authors may be portrayed as taking a critical stance by using verbs such as *disagree* or *dispute*. Finally, writers can portray authors as being neutral about the proposition using verbs such as *picture, conceive, anticipate* or *reflect* (Thompson and Ye, 1991; Hyland, 2002).

2.2. Reporting Verbs In Kazakh

In Kazakh, reporting verbs are used in both integral and non-integral citations. The examples below, taken from the corpus, demonstrate how the Kazakh reporting verb 'körsetu' (show) is used in both types of citation.

(1) *İ. ... negızderı dep ... **körsetedi.***

Vah
İ. ... that... indicate
Vah foundations

'I. Vakh indicates that the research area of the sociology of religion is: the social foundations of myth, doctrine, dogma, cult, and forms of religious associations.' (Religious Studies)

(2) ... qoldanylğandyğ **körsetedi**
) mätinderınd y

e
... in texts were used ... indicate
'The fact that the suffixes of the preposition -pan, -panın, -matın, -madın found in Old Turkic texts were used only in Oghuz language texts in later periods **indicates** that these forms are specific to the Oghuz language (Korkmaz, 2013: 44-53).' (Oriental Studies)

In the former example the emphasis is placed on the reported author (I. Vakh), and in the latter sentence on the reported message (these forms are specific to the Oghuz language).

Integral citations in Kazakh texts have been categorised according to Pickard's (1996) classification model. This model is designed to reflect the writer's intent in using the name of the cited researcher.

1. Name of researcher (NR) as: subject of the writer's sentence:

- (3) L. Ältüssera ... **körsetedi.**
...
L. Althusser show ...
...
'L. Althusser shows that any experience takes place within the framework of a certain ideology, and cannot exist outside of it.' (Philology)

2. NR as agent:

- (4) ... G.F. tarapyna ...
) Blagov n jarialanğany **atap**
a n ... **ötken**
jön.
... G.F. by ... published ... to
Blagov ... note
a wort
h

'It is worth noting that it was specially published in 1997 by the famous scholar G.F. Blagova (Samoylovich, 2005: 941).' (Oriental Studies)

3. NR as part of a possessive noun phrase:

- (5) S. eñbeginde ... **qarastyryldy.**
Asanbaeva ...
S. in the ... was
Asanbayeva work ... considered
'S. Asanbayeva's work examines the relevance of advertising language, sociolinguistic and psychological features in the study of advertising language, and the nature of advertising in the Kazakh language.' (Philology)

4. NR in other positions eg. as a direct object:

- (6) ... K.M. V.A. **qoldap,** ...
Baipaqov Kallaurdy
... K.M. V.A. supported ...
Baipakov Kallaur
'As a result of research conducted during the Soviet era, K.M. Baipakov supported V.A. Kallaur and identified Kuland with Lugovoi, ...' (Archaeology and Ethnology)

In academic texts names of authors do not always appear in the cited sentences. They might be replaced by personal pronouns such as 'ol' (he/she) and 'olar' (they) in Kazakh, and general nouns such as 'avtor(lar)' (author(s) (Example 7), 'ğalym(dar)' (scholar(s) (Example 8), and 'zertteuşı(ler)' (researcher(s) (Example 9) and so on.

- (7) GATS derektemelerdi **berip otyrdy.**
avtorlary
...
GATS data provided
authors ...
'The authors of the GATS, trying to provide the most complete source material, were forced to select the data, thus providing the most typical data in the dictionary article.' (Philosophy)

- (8) Būğan ğalymd **kelispei tanidy.**
) köptege ar **dı,** ...
n
To this scholars disagree acknowledged
many ... ge
'Many scholars disagree with this, acknowledging that innovation itself is rooted in the old, and over time, that innovation becomes tradition.' (Philosophy)

- (9) Zertteuşı **sılteme körsetken.**
jasai
otyrıp, ...
Researcher citing ... indicated
'The researcher, citing the Russian Federation's foreign policy archive, indicated that according to the Consulate of the USSR NKID (People's Commissariat of Foreign Affairs) in Kulzha, no less than 17,373 refugees returned to their former places of residence from Ili County, Xinjiang, between 1921 and 1927. ...' (Ablajei, 2014: 31). (History)

Kazakh verbs are diverse in their morphological characteristics. Kazakh features a system of aspect and tense, with several present, past, and future

tenses that distinguish forms according to volitionality, durative/iterative aspect, and evidentiality (Dotton and Wagner, 2018, p. 36). This diversity, which is found in agglutinative languages such as Kazakh, is clearly visible in the corpus concordances of verbs used in citations. Verbs, including reporting verbs, are formed by adding various affixes and by combining auxiliary verbs. Therefore, it is appropriate to first distinguish verbs with a reference meaning into two types: reporting verbs formed by various affixes and compound reporting verbs formed by auxiliary verbs. Affixes attached to reporting verbs indicate grammatical features such as aspect and tense. The structure of

complex reporting verbs is formed by combining an auxiliary verb with a head verb that has lexical meaning. Based on the corpus data, I have grouped the reporting verbs formed by the head verb into the following three models: 'head verb + auxiliary verb', 'head verb + modal word' and 'head verb + auxiliary verb + modal word'. Such modelling allows us to analyse all reporting verbs formed by one lexical head verb by grouping them. For example, the verb 'anyqta' is used with various affixes such as -p, -i, -dy, -ğan, etc. in reporting. When used in conjunction with auxiliary verbs, this verb forms compound structures such as 'anyqtap berdi', 'anyqtalyp otyr', 'anyqtai tüsti', etc. (cf. Table 1).

Table 1: Structural Models of Reporting Verbs.

Reporting verb	With affixes	Head verb + auxiliary verb	Head verb + modal word	Head verb + auxiliary verb + modal word
anyqtau (determine)	anyqtap, anyqtalyp, anyqtalady, anyqtaidy, anyqtamaidy, anyqtady, anyqtaldy, anyqtalğan, anyqtalmağan, anyqtağan, anyqtapty	anyqtalğan bolatyn, anyqtalyp otyr, anyqtai otyryp, anyqtap otyrğan, anyqtap baryp, anyqtala bastady, anyqtap körsetedi, anyqtap körsetken, anyqtap ötedi, anyqtap ötken	anyqtau mümkin emes, anyqtalğan joq, anyqtauğa bolady	anyqtalğan boluy mümkin
taldau (analyse)	taldaidy, taldady, taldap, taldağan, taldağan	taldai kelip, taldai otyryp, taldai kele, taldau jasau, taldau jasaldy, taldau jasalady, taldau jasaldy, taldau jasaidy, taldau jasai kele, taldau jasalğan, taldau jasady, taldau jaspap, taldau jasalynyp, taldau jaspap körsetpegen edi, taldau jasağanda, taldap körsetedi, taldap körsetildi, taldap syqty	taldau jasalğan joq, taldağan emes, taldau jasalğan emes	taldau boluy mümkin, taldağan boluy kerek, taldau jasaluy mumkin

Additionally, one lexical verb is used to form several compound verbs that appear in citations (cf. Table 2)

Table 2: Reporting Verbs in Compound Verbs.

Reporting verb	Compound verbs
aitu (say)	basa aitu (highlight), erekşelep aitu (emphasise), aşyp aitu (reveal), pikir aitu (express an opinion), üsynys aitu (suggest), tujyrym aitu (state), syn aitu (criticise) etc.
körsetu (show)	basa körsetu (highlight), erekşelep körsetu (emphasise), aşyp körsetu (reveal), anyqtap körsetu (identify), belgilep körsetu (indicate), ajyrata körsetu (distinguish), bölip körsetu (divide), atap körsetu (emphasise), tarqatyp körsetu (explain), etc.
otyru (sit)	berip otyru (give), körsetip otyru (show), quattai otyru (support), bailanystyryp otyru (connect, associate), eske salyp otyru (remind), belgilep otyru (mark), toqtala otyru (focus), şeşip otyru (solve), baqylai otyru (observe), siltemeler berip otyru (citing), süiene otyryp (based on), paiymdai otyryp (consider), negizge ala otyryp (based on), taldai otyryp (analysing), körsete otyryp (showing), eskere otyryp (considering), jügine otyryp (referring), atap körsete otyryp (highlighting), salystyra otyryp (comparing), nazar audara otyryp (paying attention), etc.
bıldıru (express)	qarsylyq bıldıru (object), pikir bıldıru (express an opinion), közqarasyn bıldıru (express one's point of view), qoldau bıldıru (support), oiyn bıldıru (express an opinion), etc.

beru (give)	anyqtama beru (define), túsınık beru (explain), bağa beru (evaluate, assess), jüielep beru (systematise), aqparat beru (inform, provide information), túsınıkteme beru (comment), sipattama beru (describe), túsındırıp beru (explain), mälmet beru (to provide information), män beru (pay attention), bağıt beru (direct), etc.

In terms of semantics, Kazakh reporting verbs are also diverse. One reporting verb may have several synonyms, giving writers a wide range of options for expressing themselves in a text. The meaning 'highlight' can be expressed by the verbs 'basa aitady', 'basa körsetedi', 'erekşelep aitady' and 'erekşeleidi', while the verbs 'nüsqaıdı' and 'sılteıdı' both express the meaning 'refer'. 'Ait', for example, is a frequently used reporting verb in academic Kazakh texts.

A writer could use 'de' instead of 'ait', as they have the same meaning: 'speak'. For instance:

- (10) Ğalym ...: "Bül ..." – **deıdı**.
Scholar ...: "This ..." say
'The scholar **says**: "Some of these names are characteristic of the Sak, Kanly, Uysin, and Hun eras, some of them are from the Ural-Altai language union, a group of them are from the ancient Turkic language, and the vast majority are characteristic of the Kazakh language, our indigenous words, while a small group came from Arabic, Persian, Mongolian, and Slavic (Russian, Ukrainian, Polish, etc.) languages" [4, p. 13].' (Turkology)
- (11) İu. Bromlei ... ekenn **aitady**.
Y. Bromley that say
...
'Y. Bromley **says** that the cultural integrity of members of an ethnic group is linked to common mental characteristics or national character.' (Philology)

The difference between the words 'de' and 'ait' relates to how a writer presents a claim made by an author. If a writer wants to quote an author's claim directly, the verb 'de' is used; if they want to paraphrase it, the verb 'ait' is used.

3. METHODOLOGY

A corpus of academic texts written by native Kazakh speakers was studied to investigate the use of reporting verbs in citations. Examining such corpora can enhance our understanding of the various types and purposes of citations in academic writing. Analysing them could also expand our understanding of the different types of citations used (Thompson and Tribble, 2001, p. 92).

The study employs both qualitative and quantitative approaches, comprising concordance and text analysis of a corpus of published articles. This corpus consists of 110 research articles, including 10 papers from domestic indexed journals across eleven disciplines, which were selected to represent a broad cross-section of academic practice. These disciplines are: Archaeology and Ethnology, History, Linguistics, Philosophy, Philology, Theology, Islamic Studies, Religious Studies, Turkology, Oriental Studies and Literature. Archaeology and Ethnology, History, Philosophy, Theology, Islamic Studies, Religious Studies, Turkology and Oriental Studies represent the humanities, while Linguistics, Philology and Literature are categorised as languages and literature, according to the Classifier of training programmes for personnel with higher and postgraduate education (Order, 2018). This selection justifies the corpus's representativeness by capturing key fields prominent in local scholarship, enabling a comprehensive examination of writer-reader interactions across genres and epistemologies. The articles in the corpus were published between 2000 and 2024. After excluding abstracts, references, and text associated with tables and graphics, the scanned articles produced an electronic corpus of 356,498 words. Concordance and frequency tools in AntConc (Anthony, nd) were used to search the texts for features that initiate writer-reader interactions.

I began by searching for verbs commonly used in references in Kazakh citations using AntConc's Keyword in Context tool. I then looked at sentences in which a reference was made to another author in what could be considered the standard citation form: a proper name followed by a reference number or a reference number and page number in parentheses. These references functioned as either the subject or passive agent in the clause. I also included verbs in clauses following such a citation where the subject was clearly the same quoted author (for example, where the subject pronoun referred back to the same author), as well as possessive forms of the proper name (such as 'äl Farabıdıñ közqarasy' means the opinion of Al-Farabi). Once I had identified a verb being used as a reporting verb in this way, I gathered any other instances of that verb in contexts involving reporting. I excluded subjective or adjectival uses of

reporting verbs from the analysis because the study focuses only on verbs. Therefore, forms of the verb 'ait' such as 'aitqanyñ' or 'aitylğan' were not included in the sampled concordances.

The examples from the corpus have been transliterated using QazLat, a Kazakh converter that transforms Cyrillic text into Latin letters. All the analysed sentences in this paper are original, written by Kazakh scholars and researchers, with no corrections made to punctuation or spelling.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Functions Of Reporting Verbs

I analysed the reporting verbs in Kazakh as *research acts*, *mental acts* and *discourse acts*, following the categorisation of Thompson and Ye (1991) and Hyland (2002). The types of reporting verbs vary slightly in terms of the terminology used. Thompson and Ye (1991) refer to them as *textual*, *mental* and *research acts*, whereas Hyland (2002) employs the terms 'discourse acts' and 'cognitive acts' instead of 'textual' and 'mental'. This classification is based on the type of activity to which the reporting verb refers. Verbs in the category of *research acts* represent activities or actions that are carried out in an experimental or real-world setting. They typically appear in statements of findings (e.g., observe, discover, notice, show) or procedures (e.g., analyse, calculate, assay, explore, plot, recover) (Hyland, 2002, p. 6). The examples of verbs of the research acts in Kazakh are 'taldau', 'esepteu', 'zertteu', 'jobalau', 'qalpyna keltru', 'qol jetkizu', 'alğa tartu', 'üsynu', 'däleldeu', 'dälel keltru', 'anyqtau', 'toqtalu', 'baqylau', 'talqylau', 'eskertu', 'tüyrymdau', 'mälimdeu', 'beineleu', 'nüsqu', 'tabu', 'tüsindirü', 'keltru', 'jetkizu', 'silteme beru', etc. (see more in Appendix A). The verbs of *cognition acts* (e.g., believe, conceptualise, suspect, assume, view) relate to the cognitive processes of the researcher. In Kazakh, these verbs are examples of the cognition acts category: 'senu', 'küdiktenü', 'bekitu', 'boljau', 'tarazylau', 'tanu', 'taldau', 'moiyndau', 'qabyldau', 'qorytyndylau', 'baiyptau', 'paiymdau', 'saraptau', 'kelsu', 'rastau', 'süryptau', 'baqylau', 'qorytu', 'talqylau', 'tüsünü', 'bilu', 'oilau', etc. (see more in Appendix A). *Discourse acts* involve linguistic activities and focus on the verbal expression of cognitive or research processes (e.g., ascribe, discuss, hypothesise, report, state). The verbs 'sipattau', 'talqylau', 'baiandau', 'aitu', 'tüyrymdau', 'jazu', 'qarsylyq bildiru', 'körsetu', 'atau', 'joqqa şyğaru', 'qorytu', 'tüsindirü', 'daulasu', etc. refer to the discourse acts in Kazakh.

The examples below demonstrate how the verbs

function in the research acts (Example 12), cognition acts (Example 13) and discourse acts (Example 14) in Kazakh texts:

(12) Georg öz eñbeginde taldau
Gegel ... jasağan.
Georg his in work analysed
Hegel
'Georg Hegel analysed the concept of continuity in his work.' (Philosophy)

(1 A.E. Rogo ... de tanid de boljai
3) jinski tañb p y ... p dy.
asy

A.E. ... a th recog th predi
Rogozhin sym at nise ... at ct
sky bol
of

'A.E. Rogozhinsky recognises it as a symbol of the Bukdyz tribe of the Oghuz and predicts that it represents the Turgesh-Oghuz union [44, p. 266].' (Archaeology and Ethnology)

(14) N.E. dep jazady.

Masanov ...

N.E. that write

Masanov ...

'N.E. Masanov writes that the Kazakh Khanate was founded no earlier than 1465 or 1466 [41-113,115 b].' (History)

The categorisation of reporting verbs into research, cognitive and discourse acts is not straightforward. Some verbs can be classified as both research and discourse acts. For instance, Thompson and Ye (1991, p. 370) found that the English verb 'analyse' can be categorised as either a mental or a research process, while 'agree' is considered to lie somewhere between mental and textual processes. Similar patterns can be found in Kazakh. 'Kelsu' (agree) is a cognitive act with a strong implication of mental expression, while 'qorytu' (summarise) is ambiguous between mental and research processes. 'Saraptau' (examine) may refer to intellectual or mental activities, and 'şeşu' (solve) perhaps involves all three processes. Nonetheless, the categories do offer a thorough taxonomy for differentiating the usage of reporting verbs in terms of the main components of the research process, and it is possible to consistently assign a specific meaning to all the verbs using this approach (Hyland, 2002, p. 6).

Concordance analysis of the reporting verbs in the corpus revealed a clear preference for reporting information as research acts. Most of the remaining instances were reported as discourse acts, while a small proportion were reported as cognition acts. The

range of the analysed concordances of reporting verbs in each category has shown the importance of those verbs in the citation process. Verbs in these three categories are diverse morphologically and semantically. Their morphological diversity can be explained by the agglutinative nature of the Kazakh language. Inflectional affixes, as well as auxiliary verbs, form the various grammatical forms of reporting verbs in Kazakh. One Kazakh reporting verb can be seen in various grammatical forms. For example, the verb 'ait' can be found in the forms, such as 'aita kelip', 'aitylyp keledi', 'aitqan', 'aitu kerek', 'aitsa', 'aitady', 'aita ketken', 'aita kele', 'aitylmasa kerek', 'aitady', 'aityp ötedi', and so on.

(15) O.S. **aita** dep tanidy.

Radionova **kelip**

...

O.S. noting that recognise

Radionova ...

...

'O.S. Radionova, noting that syntagmas should not be confused with sentence parts, recognises syntagmas as semantic-syntactic units in speech.' (Linguistics)

(16) ... boljamdar men tüjrymdar **aitylyp keledi.**

... and conclusions have been said
assumptions

'The sound /y-/ at the beginning of words in Turkic languages has become the subject of research by a number of linguists, especially Altaic scholars, and various assumptions and conclusions have been said regarding its history.' (Turkology)

(17) ... oısyldar **aitqan** ...

sopylyq ...

... Sufi thinkers has been said ...

...

'This has only been said by Sufi thinkers such as Hallaj Mansur, Khoja Ahmed Yasawi, and Yunus Amire in the history of Islamic civilization.' (Religious Studies)

(18) V.V. Luşai ... **aitsa,** M. Orap ...

V.V. Luschay ... say M. Orap ...

'V.V. Luschay states that words in a sentence have a certain functional role that corresponds to functional equivalence [11], while M. Orap states that words are combined with each other in a certain speech situation and acquire meaning only in context.' (Linguistics)

(19) ... bar ekeni **aita**
) anyqtamalardyñ. n **ketke**

n jön

... definitions ... ther that to say
e are worth

'It is worth noting that there are also definitions such as "Modern Arab thought" and "Modern Islamic-Arab thought" based on "Modern Islamic thought".' (Islamic Studies)

The reporting verbs such as 'korset', 'ata', 'ber', and others can also appear in various morphological forms.

4.2. Disciplinary Differences in Reporting Practices

The degree to which discourse elements can be considered discipline-specific or universal is one of the main concerns of EAP teachers. We are becoming more conscious of significant differences in how various disciplines carry out their research, defend their positions, and organise their arguments (Bartholomae, 1986; Bruffee, 1986; Becher, 1989; Hyland, 2002). Additionally, we are more aware of how academic writing's interactive and rhetorical elements convey these distinctions (Bazerman, 1988; Hyland, 1998, 1999 and 2000; MacDonald, 1993). Therefore, from a pedagogical perspective, it is necessary to inform academics and postgraduate students about these disciplinary preferences so that they might use the most traditional methods of communication with their peers. Hyland (2002) found out significant disciplinary differences in the overall use of reporting verbs, the frequencies of individual items, and the preferences for specific rhetorical categories, despite writers choosing to present cited work in generally similar ways.

While all the papers in my corpus included reporting verbs, they were far more prevalent in the history texts. All disciplines in the corpus are from the soft disciplines in the humanities and language and literature subject fields; therefore, I only draw comparisons between disciplines within these two fields. Other disciplines that more reporting verbs are used in are philosophy, philology, oriental studies and theology. Hyland (2002, pp. 12-13) noted that the higher use of citations in the soft disciplines can be explained by the following factors: (i) they usually have less established and cohesive frameworks of knowledge; (ii) they have less highly formalised and traditional codes of reporting that research (iii) they are more likely to explicitly acknowledge the role of the discipline in constructing knowledge; and (iv) they engage in more recursive patterns of investigation that involve more diverse, less predictable, and abstract subjects

than those typically found in the sciences.

As can be seen from Table 3, the density of reporting structures differs between subject groups, with one group having numbers close to each other and another group having numbers close to each other. For example, Philosophy, Philology, Oriental Studies, Theology and Religious Studies have similar

numbers of reporting verbs, whereas Archaeology and Ethnology, Islamic Studies, Linguistics and Literature have a similar range. History and Turkic Studies demonstrate substantial differences in reporting practices, exhibiting the highest and lowest numbers compared to other disciplines.

Table 3: Reporting Verbs by Discipline.

Discipline	Reporting verbs per paper	Most Frequent forms (ranked from left)	%
Archaeology and Ethnology	8.7	jazu, anyqtau, atau, zertteu, taldau	7.8
History	15.6	atau, üsynu, anyqtau, taldau, дәледеу, jazu, zertteu, talqylau	14.1
Islamic Studies	8.2	üsynu, atau, anyqtau, esepteu, alğa tartu, taldau, дәледеу, jazu	7.4
Linguistics	7.8	anyqtau, atau, taldau, zertteu, jazu	7
Literature	7.6	taldau, anyqtau, zertteu, дәледеу, atau, üsynu, esepteu	6.8
Oriental Studies	11.1	atau, üsynu, taldau, anyqtau, jazu, esepteu, alğa tartu, zertteu, дәледеу	10
Philosophy	12.8	atau, anyqtau, jazu, taldau, alğa tartu, üsynu, дәледеу, tujyrymdau	11.6
Philology	12.1	taldau, atau, anyqtau, üsynu, zertteu, дәледеу, jazu	10.9
Religious Studies	9.5	atau, üsynu, anyqtau, taldau, zertteu, saraptau	8.6
Theology	10	atau, jazu, anyqtau, alğa tartu, üsynu, tujyrymdau	9
Turkic Studies	6.8	atau, anyqtau, taldau, дәледеу	6.1
Total	110.2	atau, anyqtau, taldau, üsynu, jazu, zertteu, дәледеу	

Предлагать, Доказывать, Находить, Показывать, Описывать, Выдвигать Гипотезы, Сообщать
Suggest, Argue, Find, Show, Describe, Propose, Report

Table 3 also shows the most common forms in each discipline; alongside the percentage of reporting verbs, they accounted for. Although over 1,000 different verbs were used to introduce citations, the seven forms in the 'Totals' column constituted over a quarter of all cases. The figures suggest that writers in archaeology, ethnology, linguistics, and turkic studies relied on a more limited range of verbs, with the four or five most popular forms accounting for over 40% of all cases.

The most common verbs in the corpus were the discourse acts 'atau' (point out) (220 cases) and 'anyqtau' (define) (178), followed by the research verb 'taldau' (analyse) (129), the discourse verb 'üsynu' (propose) (125) and the discourse verb 'jazu' (write) (94). Writers in the humanities, archaeology and ethnology, theology and philosophy, for

example, greatly favoured 'jazu' (70% of cases), while 'taldau' (analyse) (82%) and 'zertteu' (study) (70%) occurred mainly in the languages and literature texts. Of the other forms which occurred not in all disciplines in the corpus, the most marked distributional imbalances were 'naqtylau' (clarify) (only five cases in three disciplines), 'saraptau' (examine) (11 cases in five disciplines) (see Chart 1), and 'bölip qarastyru' (categorise) (14 cases in seven disciplines).

'Atau' (point out), one of the most frequently used reporting verbs in the corpus (see Chart 2), acts as a discourse marker that directly supports writers' own views. This indicates that the reported information supports the writer's argument. They often express a high degree of confidence in the original author's proposition (Hyland, 2002).

Chart 1: Distribution Of the Verb 'Saraptau'.

Chart 2: Distribution Of the Verb 'Atau'.

The most common reporting verbs in Kazakh differ from those in English. In a study by Hyland (2002), for example, the verbs 'suggest', 'argue', 'find', 'show', 'describe', 'propose' and 'report' were found to be very common in reporting functions in English. Most of those verbs, for example, 'show', 'argue' and 'prove' strongly inform readers of the author's position, while 'suggest' and 'propose' report a weak stance towards the reported claims. In contrast, the seven most frequently used verbs in Kazakh are mostly of a neutral stance. The Kazakh academic community mostly uses neutral verbs such as 'aity' (say), 'ūsynu' (report), 'korsetu' (show), 'atau' (name), and 'jazu' (write) to express the positions, opinions, ideas and findings of writers and authors. Therefore, it can be concluded that writers and authors in Kazakh academic texts rely more on neutral verbs to express their positions. Strictly conveying the author's opinion is rare in Kazakh academic discourse. Further evidence of this is that disagreement with the author's opinion is very rare in the corpus texts.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The study of reporting verbs has linguistic and pedagogical implications. In this study, I examined reporting verbs from a linguistic perspective. This lays the groundwork for the subsequent study of reporting verbs for pedagogical purposes. A collection of written texts by native speakers of Kazakh provides valuable empirical data with which to determine the functions of verbs used in references, as well as their discursive patterns in academic texts. Therefore, studying reporting verbs as a linguistic means of reference paves the way for the study of other linguistic tools in academic discourse.

The reporting verbs in Kazakh are diverse in terms of structure and semantics. Structurally, they are used as a single verb with different affixes and a compound verb with auxiliary verbs. The analysed data has shown that the latter structure appears significantly more than a single use of the lexical reporting verb.

In academic discourse, the reporting verbs in Kazakh function as acts of research, cognition and discourse. The Kazakh corpus data used in this study provide significant examples to demonstrate the functional peculiarities of these verbs. These types of verbs facilitate the interaction between the reporting writer and the reported author.

Selecting an appropriate reporting verb is important because it is a key means of engaging with colleagues, positioning one's work appropriately, communicating with peers, and appealing to the interactive and epistemological understanding of one's community. Therefore, choosing a particular verb indicates not only a reported voice, but also evokes a specific context of meaning and judgement, placing the writer in a particular relationship with the reader and the reported text. This can significantly impact a reader's willingness to agree with and accept the writer's assertions.

There is obviously more work to be done. Specifically, there has not been room to talk about the typical rhetorical purposes of the reports that utilise certain verb categories, and I have not looked at evaluation in reporting verbs. Furthermore, the study only looks at research papers; it ignores other academic genres like these, reports, and students' written papers. Nevertheless, the proposed taxonomy provides a reasonably simple and practical method of mapping the differences between disciplines and genres, and determining the meaning

of various choices. Therefore, this study may contribute to a understanding of research reporting and the development of resources for inexperienced

academic writers in Kazakh, despite there being many more applications and investigations to be conducted.

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